

The Unjournal

Evaluation 2 of "How Much Would Reducing Lead Exposure Improve Children's Learning in the Developing World?"

Evaluator 2 (Unjournal, anonymous)

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This non-systematic review seeks to explore the relationship between lead exposure and children's learning outcomes by updating existing meta-analyses. Its key strengths are 1) consideration of standardized test scores for reading and mathematics 2) use of a specification curve, and different ways to assess the impacts of publication bias. Critically, a quality assessment is missing and some control choices are unmotivated. This evidence captured in the review itself is likely not causal, though the authors do examine a broader literature on the cognitive implications of lead exposure that certainly goes beyond correlational associations.

Strengths

- I view the inclusion of a specification curve very positively. This method allows authors to examine whether their conclusions are sensitive to changes in analytical approach, such as subsampling or use of controls. In a way, this allows for researchers to report their own robustness replication alongside their main 'conventional' result (e.g. meta-analytic pooled effect). It might be useful for readers to contextualize this with current wide-scale efforts in economics to mass reproduce research in top journals, which showed that 70% of effects remained significant after a robustness replication, and about half diminished in size (Brodeur et al., 2024). In other words, the inclusion of this specification curve should offer us confidence that we are looking at robustly negative and significant impacts of lead, albeit small in magnitude.
- The authors have not discussed their results in this manner, but since lead exposure can be due to macro-level policies or trends, and as such populations will be exposed to lead based on these, it may be appropriate to consider these population-level effects; as such even small effects are very important for policy (Rose, 2001)
- I am very supportive of the consideration of measures beyond IQ. IQ has been criticized as a challenging measure for young children and in some, particularly non-Western, cultural contexts. Standardized test scores for reading and mathematics are a nice addition with added applied utility, i.e. they are directly relevant for education.
- Publication bias - strong approach, especially when reporting multiple ways to account for publication bias. As is typical for such efforts, the overall pooled effect does moderately decrease. (Though I do wish this corrected-for-publication-bias effect (based on either method) would be provided in numeric terms in the report.)

Critical points

Note I see this paper as a non-systematic review and so consider it to be unfair to assess it against the standards of systematic reviews, e.g. consideration of systematic databases rather than Google Scholars, reporting standards such as inter-rater reliability measures - see PRISMA reporting standards for me). At the same time, the non-systematic approach does mean studies could have been missed or selected in a biased manner. One

way to have improved on this without an extreme time commitment is to have done a systematic search for systematic reviews in a couple of targeted databases (i.e. using 'systematic review' as a search term). There are benefits of searching for new studies systematically as well.

- The most serious concern I have is that there is no formal quality assessment (risk of bias) screening. Without this, we have no sense of whether or not this meta-analysis perpetuates the 'trash in - trash out' problem (see Egger et al. 2001). By using potentially biased data, erroneous conclusions or mis-estimation can be perpetuated and solidified. This may or may not be the case here but there is no way to tell. For instance, we have no sense of study population, recruitment strategy, attrition, power justification, robustness or validity of measures used etc.
- Inclusion criteria: studies that "have blood lead level measures from the same individuals, whether contemporaneously or from different points in time." - I assume if different time points, it would still be required that blood lead level is measured before IQ/ reading/ math, though I cannot find whether this was the specific inclusion criterion
- Extraction: "We extract any coefficient relating maternal or child blood lead levels..." there is no further mention of maternal lead beyond p.6, does this mean no studies used maternal measures or whether lead at the maternal or child level was treated the same? If the latter, I would be concerned and would prefer such a choice to better and more transparently motivated.
- "We exclude results which include blood measures for multiple ages in a model separately, as this has a different estimand: the effect of exposure at a particular age, relative to exposure at another age." - this sounds strange to me, given that likely the first available age would be comparable to all other included studies where there is bone lead measures and cognition measured fitting the inclusion criteria for time of measurement ("contemporaneously or from different points in time")
- I note in passing that from the 47s studies, 29 are in high income countries, which might suggest need for more data in LMICs - cannot make this as a strong claim, since this is not a systematic review.
- In passing as well, some figures need better labeling, e.g. include effect type directly in label.
- Specification curve - minor; perhaps could have been done in a more principled way - e.g. controls reported in stepwise manner (first each on their own, then combined), a subsampling based on country more direct comparison of high-income vs LMICs
- The second most serious concern I see is around the reporting standards. Particularly, the choice of controls is discussed very briefly and is not theoretically motivated for the reader. For instance, SES could be not only a confounder but could modify the neurotoxic effects of lead exposure. Inappropriate modeling re: SES/ other controls can lead to underestimates of the effects of lead or missattribution to the wrong risk factor (See Bellinger 2008 for more on this specifically or Judea Pearl on causality).

- Overall, taking these concerns above - lack of quality assessment, the lack of motivation for controls, and the more minor questions about timepoint inclusions - I do not personally take the evidence base captured in the review as causal. Most of the data is observational as well.
- At the same time, the discussion in Section 4 ('Assessing the role of unobserved confounders', starting p.21) is strong and helpful in focusing particularly on what kinds of work exist more broadly on the cognitive impacts of lead, and how much different studies can speak to causality (e.g. animal studies, natural experiments)

References

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